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Education of Innovation and creativity thinking on Industry 4.0 course and project

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ABSTRACT

A curriculum was developed to introduce fundamental knowledge of Industry 4.0 to students. It includes lectures of all elements in Industry 4.0, such as Internet of Things (IoT), cyber-physical systems (CPS), big data, cloud computing and so on. In addition, students were required to finish projects associated with CPS. First, students had to watch MOOCs before lectures. For the project based learning, students should use Trello, an on-line project management system, to see messages, submit their assignments, and share their ideas. Students were teamed

up at least three people before deciding the project topic. Furthermore, this curriculum integrates with creative thinking strategies, such as six thinking hats and brainstorming. When students conducted their projects, they can use creativity thinking taught in this lecture and ask for help from mentors from industry and lecturers. For instance, they visited a smart factory for mold injection and a motor factory. Students were required to write up proposals for the projects. A competition was held to let students present their CPS project products based on their creativity thinking. This curriculum successfully delivered Industry 4.0 knowledge to students by MOOCs and also applied creativity thinking strategies to students' project based learning.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Engineering Education, Physics and Engineering Education

Keywords: creativity thinking learning, Industry 4.0, cyber-physical system, project based learning

INTRODUCTION

Industry 4.0 was proposed by Germany in 2013 for intelligent manufacturing and establishing smart factories. It is the future trend for manufacturing, so engineering students should know the concept of Industry 4.0 and the way to create smart factories in future. This study is mainly concerned with investigation of students' creativity and imagination for undertaking their own projects of Cyber-Physical System (CPS), the key role of Industry 4.0. We design a curriculum including project based learning (PBL) and lectures introducing fundamental knowledge of industry 4.0. Industry 4.0 is integrated with information and communication technology (ICT) data for manufacturing technology. CPS is a term that led to the advancement of Internet of Things implementations and also introduces cooperation among CPS elements, by integrating computational resources [1]. It is also a system that involves a high degree of complexity, temporal scales, and highly networked communications [2]. It has computational and physical components [2]. It is connected with internet and its users. The aim of Industry 4.0 is to utilize CPS to establish a smart factory.

The curriculum we designed has been conducting to promote student interest in the Science, Technology and Mathematics (STEM) fields. STEM education can be seen as a pipeline beginning in early education, extending through college [3]. Today, we have lots of PBL courses applied to CPS. For instance, the future applications of CPS use many elements, such as embedded systems, high speed network, cloud computing and big data technology [4]. This PBL course was motivated and designed by the Urban Information Systems [4].

Since Industry 4.0 is a new concept, there are rare examples to follow or to duplicate. Therefore, students needs to know the way to create various new CPS for a smart factory. In this curriculum, students not only learned fundamental knowledge about industry 4.0, but also needed to implement the project integrated with creative thinking strategy. Moreover, we used the creative thinking strategies, such as "Six Thinking Hat" [5] and "Brainstorming" [6]. We conducted those activities to cultivate their creativity. We had the quizzes for students to know if they understood the units or not in the end of each class.

1 CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT

1.1 Intra-curricular

MOOCs was adopted to deliver fundamental knowledge of Industry 4.0 to students. Before the class started, students were required to watch MOOCs online videos in advance. Topics of MOOCs includes Internet of Things (IoT), cyber-physical systems (CPS), big data, cloud computing and so on. Lecturers addressed the knowledge what they learned in MOOCs during class. Quizzes were given to students for checking what they have learned and reviewed the contents in MOOCs. The on-line quiz system we used is called “Kahoot”, a platform of mobile learning. It can let students interact with teachers in the lecture room. This curriculum also invited many prestigious mentors from industry to lecture part of topics. Mentors not only shared their experiences, but also taught a lot of professional knowledge of Industry 4.0.

Furthermore, we used two creative thinking strategies that could help students think as they were doing their projects. The strategies used are “Six Thinking Hat” and “Brainstorming”. The reason for choosing two creative thinking strategies is because we can use brainstorming activities to help students work out the new idea for CPS, and use Six Thinking Hat to help students check out whether this idea is good or not. These two strategies might be both used in the activities. They can cultivate students’ creativity and imagination. The activities integrated with game based learning and team cooperation. Students needed to discuss with each other and wrote down their ideas in activities. We designed different topics so that we could train students to use those two strategies in those topics. Since students watched MOOCs videos in advance, they could discuss with one another and shared their thoughts every week in difference topic. When students used “Six Thinking Hat”, they often considered advantages and disadvantages on a topic. Moreover, students would use “Brainstorming” to solve questions. Figures 1 & 2 show the activity during lecture:

Fig. 1. Brainstorming activity.

Fig. 2. Brainstorming activity.

The whole schedule of the curriculum is shown as following:

Table 1. Overview of the schedule of the course.

Week	Before class	In class	Project
1		Introduction	

Week	Before class	In class	Project
2			
3			
4		Embedded System & Brainstorming	Team up
5	MOOCs	Sensor & Brainstorming	Choose topics
6	A technical visit in companies		
7	MOOCs	Innovation and applications of IoT & Brainstorming	
8	MOOCs	CPS system & Six thinking hats	
9		Six thinking hats	Presentation of midterm report
10		Discussion	
11		Big data and cloud computing & Six thinking hats	
12		Project implementation	
13		Process automation and special processing	
14		Discussion	
15		Project implementation	
16		Project implementation	
17		Six thinking hats	
18		Presentation of final report	

Besides, we used the project management platform called “Trello” in PBL. Students could get information and post their homework on Trello (Fig. 3). If students had any questions, they could post a message, and a lecturer would answer questions in the system. Trello is just like an interactive bulletin board. It can help students catch information in their group and share every files or pictures they want. It is a convenient platform piling up whole information we have.

Fig. 3. Trello- Industry 4.0.

1.2 Extra-curricular

We also organized industry visits in this curriculum, as shown in Fig. 4. It shows that students had technical tours in a moto company and the Industry 4.0 implementation center of our university and discussed with mentors. Before the visit, each team needed to list several questions they wanted to ask mentors. After arriving at the companies, mentors introduced the company or the center and offered tours around the factory of the company. According to the questions that students proposed, mentors explained one after another, sharing their experiences, so students can learn the details about whole the process through the visit.

Students visited a moto company and attended their lecture

Students visited the Industry 4.0 implementation center in our campus.

Fig. 4. Company visiting.

1.3 PBL

After understanding the knowledge of industry 4.0 and creativity thinking strategies, we expect students could use what we taught in their projects. In this curriculum, we cooperated with three companies. Each group had their topics and they could contact with their mentors from those three companies to report their progress regularly. Students were required to make midterm and final presentations. In the midterm presentation, students needed to write proposals and reported during lecture. The referees would give students a number of comments. The midterm proposal template is defined as following:

- Abstract
- Research Motivation
- Research Objectives
- Programme Design
- Experiment Equipment and Budget Planning
- Difficulty and Solution
- Teamwork
- Evaluation
- References.

Moreover, students finished projects, delivering presentations in final exam (Figs. 5 to 8). Figures 5 to 8 show students' CPS products, which include a smart storage machine, an Automatic Guided Vehicle (AGV), and a game bike. The smart storage machine included the device scanning QR Code and the motor deciding position of every item. The AGV is referred to Arduino as a control panel and uses an infrared sensor to follow the destination. The game bike is integrated with teaching strategy and game

scene. According to these projects we just mentioned, they correspond with CPS and creativity thinking strategies.

Students must design the posters showing the characteristics about their CPS projects for oral presentation. In addition to the CPS projects, students also needed to write marketing proposals. It can help students understand how to sell their CPS products and know market requirements. The marketing proposal template is defined as following:

- Abstract
- SWOT Analysis
- Customer
- Product Introduction and Characteristics
- The Marketing Theory of 4Ps
- Conclusion.

Fig. 5. Smart storage machine

Fig. 6. Automatic Guided Vehicle

Fig. 7. Game bike

Fig. 8. Automatic Guided Vehicle (AGV)

According to the templates we mentioned, it benefits students for making products by themselves and learn how to use creativity thinking strategies to help them generate ideas.

2 EVALUATION

In this project, in order to know students' background, habits, and interests, pre-test and post-test were undertaken. Both questionnaire and interview were used in the tests. The result of questionnaire shows students' learning outcome, suggestion, and the level of understanding of the creativity thinking strategies in this curriculum.

Regarding the evaluation in this curriculum, we decided the grade criteria in midterm and final presentations. In the midterm presentation, we used five items to evaluate

students' proposals. We invited two mentors to judge the proposals. In final exam, peer-evaluation was adopted. It is because students had the same experience and they knew what kind of project would be the best and useful. Furthermore, we gave students four different kinds of color stickers. They could put the stickers to four zones of a poster, which they thought is the best part of the projects. The four zones that are called creativity, presentation, technique, and potential. It is shown on table 2:

Table 2. Evaluation between Midterm and Final Exam

Evaluation in Midterm	Evaluation in Final
Logic	creativity
Technique	presentation
Curiosity	technique
Feasibility	potential
Application of CPS	Development in the future

Figures 9 shows students' final poster presentation. Results and discussion are reported in other papers in this session.

Fig. 9. Poster Presentation

3 CONCLUSIONS

This curriculum includes a variety of learning elements, such as MOOCs, creativity thinking strategies, lectures, project based learning, etc. This paper shows the results of students' projects and various interactive course developments. According to the curriculum we just mentioned, this proposed curriculum can cultivate students' imagination and creativity. Students could learn lots of knowledge about industry 4.0 in this curriculum. We also designed the creativity activity so that it could inspire students' curiosity and imagination. This developed curriculum successfully delivered knowledge of industry 4.0 to students and also opportunities to implement a CPS project based on creativity thinking.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Zanni. (2015), *Cyber-physical systems and smart cities*, IBM Corporation 2015, U.S.A, pp. 1-8.
- [2] National Institute of Standards and Technology (2013). *Foundation for innovation in cyber-physical system*. Retrieved from <https://www.nist.gov/sites/default/files/documents/el/CPS-WorkshopReport-1-30-13-Final.pdf>
- [3] V. Gadepally, A. Krishnamurthy, U. Ozguner. (2014), A Hands-on Education Program on Cyber Physical Systems for High School Students, *Journal of Computational Science Education*, Vol.3, No.2, pp.11-17.
- [4] Y. Kim, A. Chen, S. Jadhav, CS. Gloster, T. Le, and P. Hsu (2016), *Project based Courses in Control Cyber Physical System Co-Design*, Proc. WESE 2016, Martin Edin Grimheden, USA, no.4.
- [5] De Bono, Edward (1985). *Six Thinking Hats: An Essential Approach to Business Management*. Little, Brown, & Company. ISBN 0-316-17791-1 (hardback) and 0316178314 (paperback).
- [6] Osborn, A.F. (1963) *Applied imagination: Principles and procedures of creative problem solving* (Third Revised Edition). New York, NY: Charles Scribner's Sons.